

Σαλαμίς, σαῶλαμᾶνδρα (“salamander”), σαλαμίνθη (“spider”),
σαῶλάμβη / σαῶλάβη (“chimney, vent-hole”), θᾶλαμος , θόλος , Σάλμοξις /
Ζάλμοξις, Σαλμωνεύς, ἀνδράχλη, ἀνδράχνη, ἄνθραξ , κορίανδρον *and more*

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After considering various scenarios, I have come to the conclusion that the name of the Ancient Greek island of Σαλαμίς (Salamis) referred/refers to the curved shape of the island, which is similar to that of a lizard in a doubled over position, a curled position (e.g. a lizard that is in a fetal position) or to a short snake in such a position. Σαλαμίς was also the name of a nymph in Greek mythology¹: she was the daughter of the river-god Asopus and of Metope, daughter of Ladon, another river-god. Snakes were often associated with bodies of water in Greek myth and in the mythologies of all human cultures, and Salamis may have originally been a nymph that appeared as both human and water-snake.

This similarity of the shape of the island to the shape of a doubled over lizard is reportedly referenced in Culuris/Κούλουρη (*Koulouri*), a name for the island which is first attested in the year 1204 AD. A scholar named William Miller, in his 1908 book *The Latins in the Levant, a history of Frankish Greece (1204-1566)*, says that Culuris meant “Lizard” (see page 18 of his book ²), and this name was given to the island/was used for the island because of the island’s shape: which is like that of a short-tailed lizard that has curled itself/doubled itself over into a fetal position. From at least the 13th century until the 19th century, the town, the island, and the bay of Salamis were called *Koulouri* (Κούλουρη). The ancient name Salamis was revived in the 19th century. The name Koulouri is still used informally for the town. The island is known in Arvanitika as Κ8λλ8ρι (“Kulluri”).

Κούλουρη is derived from Ancient Greek κόλουρος , meaning “dock-tailed, stump-tailed”, a compound of Ancient Greek κόλος (“docked”) and οὐρά (“tail; rear”). If Miller was right that the name of the island Culuris/Κούλουρη (*Koulouri*) meant/means “lizard”---and he seems to imply that he heard this first-hand himself during his travels in Greece, that Culuris/Κούλουρη means “lizard”---then I think that would be because most (or all?) lizards can snap off their tail when they need to, and the tail then grows back bit by bit, over some time; that phenomenon of snapped-off lizard tails growing back bit by bit over time must be the reason why Culuris/Κούλουρη (*Koulouri*), which literally means “dock-tailed”, would come to be applied to lizards; because otherwise, when their tails are full-grown, most/many lizards have quite long and often very long tails, and in those cases “dock-tailed” would not be appropriate.

Three points to review: 1) Miller’s statement that Culuris meant “Lizard” due to the shape of the island; 2) the similarity of Salamis to the Ancient Greek word σαῶλαμᾶνδρα (“the fire salamander”) which is of highly disputed and debated etymology and is usually considered a Pre-Greek word; and 3) the etymology of Σαλαμίς itself being disputed and debated and often considered Pre-Greek; considering a number of factors in addition to these three points (factors which I will discuss in this paper), I posit that Salamis meant either “Curved, bent” or “lizard, snake”; and if it meant “lizard,

1 See [Salamis \(mythology\) - Wikipedia](#) .

2 The book and the specific page should be accessible at this link: [The Latins in the Levant, a history of Frankish Greece \(1204-1566\) : Miller, William, 1864-1945 : Free Download, Borrow, and Streaming : Internet Archive](#)

snake”, those meanings quite surely derive from the earlier meanings “curved, bent”, as I will try to show further during my discussion of σᾶλᾶμᾶνδρᾶ, σαλαμίνθη, σαλάμβη /σαλάβη, θᾶλᾶμος and θόλος and more.

In numerous languages of the world, there are words for “snake” and/or “lizard” which derive from “to curve, bend”: one example is Pali bhujaga (“snake”) which derives Pali bhujā (“crooked”, “bent”) plus Pali -ga (“going”), thus the Pali snake word bhujaga literally means “crooked-goer”; Pali bhujā (“bending, crooked; arm”) derives from Sanskrit bhújā, which had polysemy like many Sanskrit words: “arm; breast; hand; trunk of an elephant; branch, bough; bending, curve, coil (of a serpent)”, from PIE **b^hewǵh-*, “to bend, curve, arch”.

My primary theory is that σᾶλᾶμᾶνδρᾶ meant “fire lizard/fire snake”: σᾶλᾶμ=“lizard, snake” as detailed above, from “to curve, bend” as I will detail further in this paper; and ᾶνδρᾶ meant “fire; fiery; red” (likely all three of these meanings would be from the older meaning “bright”, as I will detail later), cognate to Ancient Greek ᾶνθραξ, which meant “charcoal; a deep red precious stone, a carbuncle; an abscess, a boil”, with all meanings I posit coming from “fiery, burning” or “red” (the abscess/boil meanings most likely come from the red color of boils). The word ᾶνθραξ is of unknown etymology and unknown origin, and is already considered to likely be from a Mediterranean substrate. My etymology of σᾶλᾶμᾶνδρᾶ as “fire-lizard”, in the manner that I have described, I think is far better than a very unlikely etymology I have seen positing that σᾶλᾶμᾶνδρᾶ is cognate with Basque sugelandila (=“lizard”), sugeandila (“lizard”), etc.

A theory that ᾶνθραξ is cognate with some Indo-Iranian words meaning “blind, dark” (see for example Sanskrit andhá “blind, dark” from Proto-Indo-Iranian **(H)and^hás* “blind”, perhaps from a PIE root having the form **h₂end^h-ó-s*, which would be **h₂end^h-* plus the PIE suffix *-ós*) is most likely wrong, even though charcoal is black: but the other meanings of ᾶνθραξ besides charcoal indicate the older meaning was “fiery, burning” or “red”, not “black, dark”. Compare Ancient Greek κᾶνδαρος “charcoal” from PIE **(s)kand-* “to shine, glow, burn(?)”. Lubotsky (1999) does not mention ᾶνθραξ at all when discussing cognates and likely cognates of Sanskrit andhá outside of Indo-Iranian³. I’m not sure what meaning(s)--if any--are given for this **h₂end^h-* from which Sanskrit andhá and its Indo-Iranian cognates are posited to derive. Do they mean PIE **h₂end^h-*, “to bloom”? The semantics seems very unlikely, in fact opposite, since “bloom” is linked with “bright”, not “dark, black”. The unlikely semantics is why it also posited that Indo-Iranian **(H)and^hás* “blind” is of Non-IE/BMAC origin.

Indisputable evidence that there was an Ancient Greek/Pre-Greek Andra as a form of Anthra- (found in ᾶνθραξ) is found in Ancient Greek ᾶνδράχλη=“warming-pan, brazier”, attested in Suda’s fragments of Eustathius’ writings, 1571.25; and I’m sure that this Andra form of Anthra-/ is also found in ᾶνδράχλη having the meaning “the Greek strawberry tree, *Arbutus andrachne*” (sometimes called the “wild strawberry”, but unlike strawberries, it is a tree, not a ground-covering plant), which has very red berries, of a very rich red color. ᾶνδράχλη is a variant of ᾶνδράχνη; according to Frisk’s Etymological dictionary of Ancient Greek, ᾶνδράχλη is a dissimilation of ᾶνδράχνη, which Frisk concludes is the older form; Frisk gives no etymology. This word has baffled so many etymologists for so long because they didn’t realize that there were two identically written and identically pronounced ᾶνδράχλη / ᾶνδραχλος / ᾶνδράχνη / ᾶνδραχνος words having different etymologies (though the root may ultimately be the same, as I will detail later, making it even more understandable why the forms are identical). The ᾶνδράχλη / ᾶνδραχλος / ᾶνδράχνη / ᾶνδραχνος words which refer to purslane and to some additional plants related to purslane, I will detail the etymology of those words later in this

3 see Lubotsky, Alexander, *The Indo-Iranian substratum*, 1999.

section of this paper, where I will also discuss the -χλη/-χνη portion of the words, which I conclude is most likely a suffix, a Pre-Greek suffix apparently.

The association of salamanders with fire is first attested in Aristotle (I know of no earlier indication anywhere in the world yet) and was later detailed by Pliny (Plinius), and was a big part of at least late Greco-Roman and subsequent belief in Europe and from there imported to other parts of the world⁴. I posit that the association comes primarily from the black mottled with yellow and sometimes black mottled with orange or black mottled with red colors of the salamander, and secondarily (but a very close second factor) from a factor that has already been noted: salamanders are moist and live next to water and are amphibious, and water extinguishes fire, so the combination of fiery colors and moist skin and living near water worked on people's imaginations; I doubt that the substance that salamanders exude can allow them to survive any more significant contact with flames or great heat, even though the substances that they exude keeps their skin moist and prevents them from drying out.

Salamanders often live in old logs on the forest floor, and when some of those logs with at least one salamander living in them was then tossed by humans on a fire: the salamander would come out and scurry away before the flames got too close and too hot; combine this scene with the colors of the fire salamander, and the wet skin and amphibious nature, and it's little wonder how the belief arose.

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https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cultural_depictions_of_salamanders for more about the association of salamanders (especially the fire salamander, and I'm sure the fire salamander is the source of such beliefs) with fire in human belief: it was a big thing, in fact a pretty big industry too. And it surely predates Aristotle's record of it (he himself doubted the legends) by many centuries, in fact probably by many millenia. Linguistically, I have checked the etymologies of well over a dozen salamander words worldwide and excluding σἄλᾰμᾰνδρᾰ I have found none besides possibly Persian samandar which may contain a reference to fire, which is not problematic to my theory since the fire salamander is not found outside of Europe (not even in Turkey) and the fire association surely came from the coloring of the fire salamander. Persian samandar has long been considered a compound of Persian sām="fire, flame" and Persian andar="inside" by most Persian dictionaries, but it could well be a loan from Ancient Greek, but the Ancient Greek cannot possibly be from Persian linguistically nor would that make sense, since the fire salamander is not found outside Europe and surely the fire association comes from the fire salamander.

My secondary theory is that σἄλᾰμᾰνδρᾰ meant "fat lizard/fat snake": the fire salamander looks like a fat lizard, like a toad lizard. In this case, ᾰνδρᾰ would be a different, additional ᾰνδρᾰ word in Ancient Greek/Pre-Greek that I conclude meant "fat, swollen", a word that I conclude I have found in Ancient Greek ᾰνδρᾰνον / ᾰνδρᾰνον meaning "raised bank by the side of a river or ditch; dyke; border, edge, of the sea; ball of the hand from whence the thumb projects", and in the ᾰνδρᾰχλη / ᾰνδρᾰχλος / ᾰνδρᾰχνη / ᾰνδρᾰχνος words when they refer to common purslane (*Portulaca oleracea*, has yellow flowers and succulent thick, fat leaves) and to other species of purslane (wild purslane, *Euphorbia peplis*, which has succulent leaves and purple stems, flowers are not red nor reddish; not to be confused with *Euphorbia peplus*, a spurge which has very thin, floppy, non-succulent leaves) and to some plants closely related to or closely resembling purslane: *Phedimus stellatus/Sedum stellatum* (succulent fat leaves; flowers are white, pink or a light purplish shade); *Sedum telephium* (has fat thick leaves that look like purslane leaves, flowers are sometimes white sometimes reddish); *Sedum cepaea* (has fat succulent leaves and pale pinkish white flowers). Purslanes are succulent plants with thick, fleshy fat

4 I have not yet seen evidence that the belief was natively found outside of Europe.

leaves of the succulent type, and in Romanian the word for purslane is *iarbă grasă* meaning “fat grass” (*iarbă*=“grass”; *grasă*=“fat”). Common purslane has yellow flowers, and stems of a not-eye-catching subdued reddish hue: there’s not enough red on any of these plants enumerated in this paragraph to provoke someone to name these plants after anything red on a few of them. Some varieties of purslane (not necessarily found in Ancient Greece or known to the peoples who lived in that part of the world) have conspicuous orange-red flowers, but not the various species described here. I know of no word for purslane plants which derives “red” or “fiery”, and these ones surely do not: there were two different sets of ἀνδράχλη / ἀνδραχλος / ἀνδράχνη / ἄνδραχνος words having different etymologies, but they may ultimately all go back to an ancient root that meant “to swell”, from whence on one hand developed “fat, swollen” and on the other hand “blooming, bright”: I have found some words for “bright” that derive from “to swell, to beam out, to expand out”: including Ancient Greek ἄνθος “flower, blossom, bloom, peak; brightness, brilliance”, and ἄνθος derives from PIE **h₂end^{h-}*, “to bloom”.

The taste of the purslane is not a bitter nor burning taste, nor do these plants cause burning rashes, so the taste of these plants do not connect them to “fire”, nor do they cause any burning of the skin, etc.

Since in one set of the ἀνδράχνη words, *andra*=“fire, red” and in the other set of ἀνδράχνη words, *andra*=“fat”, the function the suffix *χνη/χλη/χλος/χνος* seems to be only to make a certain type of noun from a noun (“fire”; “red”) or adjective (“fiery; red; fat, thick”). So it appears that at least in these ἀνδράχνη words *χνη/χλη/χλος/χνος* are only suffixes; it’s likely that in some other Ancient Greek words with such terminations, the terminations are again only suffixes; very likely they are Pre-Greek suffixes.

Back now trying to determine the roots or root of *andra* (“fire; fiery; red”) and *andra* “fat, swollen, thick”: it is known from many examples in many language families, including IE, that “bright” easily leads to “red”, and “bright” is sometimes the source of words meaning “fire”. Note also boils which are swollen and red; and many other body ailments which manifest as both red and swollen; and note the red/reddish swollen disk of the sun at dawn, swelling up over the horizon. So PIE **h₂end^{h-}*, “to bloom”, was probably originally **h₂end^{h-}*, “to swell”, similar to PIE **h₃eyd-*, “to swell”, from which, according to a theory I found in a work published in 1992⁵, likely derives Proto-Indo-Iranian **Índras*, source of the Indo-Aryan god Indra: the idea published was that the meaning “strong” developed from “to swell” (as usually happens), and Indra meant “the Strong one”; my addition to that is that Indra may have meant “strong”, “blooming” and “bright”, which all fit a sky-god/storm-god who corresponds to Zeus, Jupiter, Thor, the Daco-Thracian Salmoxis/Zalmoxis, et al.

If Indra derives from the root **h₂end^{h-}*, “to swell, bloom, bright” that I described above, it would have to be via a language that was different from Sanskrit, because Sanskrit *ándhas*=“Soma, grass, herb” derives from **h₂end^{h-}*, “to bloom”.

There is also an Ancient Greek word *σάκανδρος* whose etymology was only partially understood; the word referred to the pudenda muliebria; that is to say: referred specifically to the pubic mound and bush (unless clean-shaven or not yet having pubes) of the outer vagina (*pudenda*=the external genitalia), to the Venus Mound; and at least eventually (very soon) also including the labias of the vagina; the word is attested in one of Aristophanes’ plays, a bawdy, raunchy comedy play called

⁵ Mayrhofer, Manfred (1992) *Etymologisches Wörterbuch des Altindoarischen* [Etymological Dictionary of Old Indo-Aryan], volume 1, Heidelberg: Carl Winter Universitätsverlag, pages 192-93

Lysistrata, originally performed in classical Athens in 411 BC. I conclude that the first element σάκ- derives from Ancient Greek σάκκος/σάκος = "coarse cloth of hair, especially goat's hair", an Ancient Greek word of disputed etymology and disputed geographical origin (Beekes concludes that it's most likely from Semitic; others disagree). While I posit that the ανδρος of σάκανδρος is cognate with άνδηρον / άνδειρον, and I conclude that the ανδρος of σάκανδρος meant "a mound" referring to the Venus Mound: thus σάκανδρος literally and in the strict sense means a bushy Venus mound/a bushy pudenda muliebria.

The passage in Lysistrata---the only surviving attestation of this word---is about a man saying that if the woman kicks up her leg, he will see her sakandros, without him using any other words indicating the hair on her pudenda: the woman replies that despite her age, he will see that her pudenda is well-plucked, not overgrown with a shaggy bush; so the passage in Aristophanes' Lysistrata directly indicates my etymology: read the passage and you will see that it really is as if σάκανδρος means a bushy pudenda (the pudenda being the Venus Mound plus the labias): and I think that is because the original sense was "Coarse-haired Mound", a comedic and disparaging slur for the pudenda muliebria.

Basque andre/andra meaning "woman, wife, lady" are considered to be (in the references I read) from the form andere, a form which is also attested, in Basque and in Aquitanian. I hypothesize these Basque and Aquitanian words may be from the earlier meaning "fat, swollen", referring especially to the breasts of women and older girls, breasts which produce milk after they give birth; but also referring to the buttocks and hips of many women and older girls; recall also the statuette of the Venus of Willendorf. For the semantics, see PIE *peyh₂- "to swell (with milk), to be swollen, fat", a root from which derive many IE words; and a root which has been posited to be the root of Proto-Germanic *faimô , "maiden, girl". I have to study this Basque and Aquitanian word more, and study whether And- can be ancient in those languages.

The name of Andros island in the Aegean sea may not be from the Ancient Greek word meaning "man" but instead maybe somehow from this Pre-Greek root meaning "to swell; to swell up": perhaps in reference to the very mountainous terrain of the island (the island does not have a round shape). A derivation from the meaning "fire" or "red" doesn't at present seem likely for the island. See the last section of this paper for another Ancient Greek word (which is attested in a number of variants) that likely contains this Andr-/Andn meaning "swollen, fat, thick".

Now I will return to Salam/Thalam and detail the further excellent indications that Salam/Thalam="to curve, bend" in at least a handful of Ancient Greek words which very likely derive from a Pre-Greek language, likely from a Pre-Greek language that was either descended from Proto-Indo-European or descended from a very close sister/brother language of Proto-Indo-European.

Part 2: further indications that Salam- in Pre-Greek="To curve, to bend"

Another Ancient Greek word of unknown etymology and which is also probably Pre-Greek is σάλάμβη /σαλάβη = "vent-hole, chimney", which I think derives from "hole" in turn from "to curve, bend", based on

1) my above determination that there was an Ancient Greek/Pre-Greek Salam="to curve, bend", for the reasons discussed above;

2) based on the Ancient Greek words κύπη="hole, cavity, hollow", from PIE *kew, "to bend, curve, arch; to swell, bulge"; and γύπη meaning "vulture's nest", "a hole", "a hollow, cavity", "a

corner, angle”⁶, and γυπάριον=“nest, cranny”, both from PIE *gew, “to bend, curve, arch; to swell, bulge”

3) based on another Ancient Greek word of unknown etymology, θάλαμος (=an inner chamber, a room, a bedroom; a store-room) which Beekes et al. think is probably Pre-Greek, and Beekes posited that θάλαμος is cognate with θόλος (=a round building with conical roof, a rotunda; a vaulted steam-bath; a bandage for the head)⁷, another Ancient Greek word of unknown etymology which Beekes and other experts think is probably Pre-Greek; for the occasional TH ~ S variation in Ancient Greek words, the most famous example to reference is θάλασσα vis-à-vis Laconian Greek σάλασσα

4) based on an Ancient Greek word first attested in Byzantine Greek, σαλαμίνθη, meaning “spider”, which I posit derives from “to curve, bend” just as the Germanic words coppe, kobbe, cob (etc.) meaning “spider” by consensus derive from PIE *gew, “to bend, curve, arch”, and therefore that particular set of Germanic spider words are cognate with Ancient Greek γύπη and γυπάριον. Similarly, Ancient Greek ράξ (“grape; berry; the bulb of the fingertips”) also referred to a type of spider, because of the round shape of the abdomen, as seen with most spiders. The fact that σαλαμίνθη has the Pre-Greek suffix “ίνθη” corroborates the other indications that the element σαλαμ- as well is most likely from Pre-Greek.

Someone may say that σάλαμβη and σαλάβη derive from the meaning “fire” (I have seen no one saying that), as does Ottoman Turkish “ocak”, which means “fireplace; hearth; chimney” etc. but derives from the older meaning “fire”, from Proto-Turkic *ōt = “fire”; and since σάλαμάνδρα referred to the fire salamander (the fire salamander was believed by some peoples at some points in ancient times to be able to dwell/remain in fire without being burned), someone may say that Salam=“fire”: I myself seem to be the first person in history to have posited that Salam- in σάλαμάνδρα meant “fire”, a theory I first published in December 2020 or January 2021. However, the theory that Salam=“fire” would leave out σαλαμίνθη, since it is very unlikely for a word meaning “spider” to derive from “fire” or “burning”: maybe if the reference was to some spider-induced rashes that caused a burning sensation, but even if some spider-induced rashes of the region and time in question did produce a burning sensation---which I have not confirmed yet---It is still a very unlikely scenario. It would also be unlikely for the island name Salamis to derive from “fire” or “burning”, despite the occasional forest fire on the island through the centuries (but have forest fires occurred often enough to motivate a fiery name for the island? Probably not).

Positing that σάλαμβη and σαλάβη derive from Salam or Sala=“fire” also forces (unless we consider σάλαμβη/σαλάβη and σάλαμάνδρα to be unrelated in all their parts) the Andra or Mandra (according to my theory, it’s Andra, not Mandra) in σάλαμάνδρα to have certain meanings for which no good support can be found in the Ancient Greek vocabulary or any other relevant language: “striker, slayer, extinguisher” (if one were to suppose “fire-slayer, fire-striker, fire-extinguisher”: because it was often believed that fire salamanders could extinguish fires); “dwelling, abiding” (“fire-dweller”); “suited, adjusted, acclimated; fitted to” (“fire-acclimated”, “fire-suited”, etc.); “loving” (“fire-loving”/“fire-lover”); “lizard, snake” (“fire-lizard; fire-snake”: Yes, I conclude that σάλαμάνδρα meant “fire-lizard”, but only if Salam=lizard, snake, not Andra; I conclude that Andra very likely meant “fire”); “born” (“fire-born”, as fire salamanders were sometimes believed to be born in fire) and so on. So we see that Salam=“to curve, bend” works better. Salam=“Fire” also doesn’t match θάλαμος and θόλος, forcing the exclusion of those words.

6 See the LSJ entry for γύπη on the Perseus Digital Library: [Henry George Liddell, Robert Scott, A Greek-English Lexicon, γύπη \(tufts.edu\)](#).

7 See Beekes, Robert S. P. (2010) *Etymological Dictionary of Greek* (Leiden Indo-European Etymological Dictionary Series; 10), volume I, with the assistance of Lucien van Beek, Leiden, Boston: Brill, → ISBN, page 530.

Positing that σᾶλάβη and σαλάβη derives from “to cut, to scratch” works for the “chimney” and “vent-hole” meanings, as a passage that has been cut open: see Swedish skorsten meaning “chimney, flue”, deriving from Proto-Germanic *skeran, “to cut”, from PIE *(s)ker-, “to cut”. And that would be compatible with Σαλαμῖς = “lizard”, since a number of IE words for “lizard” derive from “digger” in turn from “to cut, scratch/sharp”: because lizards usually have long curved claws that look like the claws of for example badgers, who dig/burrow underground extensively, so many people imagined that lizards used their claws to dig/burrow, besides any other uses for their claws.

The equation salam=“to cut, to scratch” would also work for σᾶλᾶμᾶνδρᾶ, since Salam would mean “lizard” though deriving from “digger”; then we would still have Salam=“lizard” and Andra=“fire” or Andra=“fat”. The equation salam=“to cut, to scratch” would also work for σαλαμίνθη (“spider”), since a number of words for spiders, arachnids, insects, arthropods, tc. derive from “to bite” or from “to scratch, cut”, because their bites leave cuts on the skin (many spiders don’t bite people, but some spider words do derive from “biter” and/or “to cut, scratch”). But “to cut, to scratch” doesn’t match θᾶλᾶμος nor θόλος, and we would again have to exclude them.

An interesting item that likely indicates that σᾶλάβη / σαλάβη are in fact cognate with θᾶλᾶμος and θόλος is the correspondence of Ancient Greek κάμῖνος (“oven, furnace, kiln; flue for warming a room”) and Ancient Greek κᾶμᾶρᾶ (“room”; compare Thamos and Tholos above), which have both been already posited to derive from PIE *kh₂em- “to bend, to curve; smooth”; but others think they are not cognates, and that κάμῖνος is instead cognate with Proto-Slavic *kamy, “stone”, which sounds good semantically; but so does the derivation from “chamber<to bend, curve”.

While positing that Salamis (*lizard) and σαλαμίνθη (spider) are both from “to cling” or “to grasp” or “to climb” works for those two creatures/two words well since both spiders and many (or all?) lizards can climb up walls and cling to vertically straight walls, and both can cling to a ceiling and walk across it upside down (at least, many species of lizards can); but such a root-meaning would probably exclude all the other words except σᾶλᾶμᾶνδρᾶ, since we would still have Salam=“lizard”, with lizard deriving from “to cling” or “to grasp”.

A possibility I considered over a year ago is that σᾶλᾶμᾶνδρᾶ and σαλαμίνθη (“spider”) derive from a Salam- that meant “venomous, poisonous”, with “venomous, poisonous” deriving from “that which strikes”---that would work okay for only those two words however (even though only a small number of spiders in the Ancient Greek/Pre-Greek world were venomous---which ones, maybe I will find out by my next update---and the toxin emitted from fire salamander skin may not be so dangerous to humans in reality; but in folkore and myth, the lethality and power of salamander toxin was greatly exaggerated; check that article about salamanders in myth and legend if you are not familiar with that), and since it would work okay for only those two words, I doubt that that is the case. While “venomous” would not work so good for salamis=“lizard” (I doubt that any lizards in that part of Europe or in any part of Europe are venomous) there are indications that many people of the past believed that at least some lizards are venomous, but that belief may have been only a minority belief among some people of the past. But one may say that salamis “lizard” came from salamis “snake”, in turn from salamis=“venomous”. So then we would have Salam=“lizard (deriving from snake, in turn from venomous)” and Andra=“fire”, which would again give “Fire lizard”. But if Salam in Salamandra meant “venomous” but not “snake” nor “lizard” nor “toad”, then what would Andra mean? The meanings that Andra had in Pre-Greek: “something swollen; mound, embankment, fat, thick” on the one hand and “fire, fiery, red” don’t provide a likely source for the semantic “lizard” nor “snake” to arise.

My etymology of σαλαμάνδρα as “fire-lizard”, in the manner that I have described (Salam=“lizard”, andra=“fire”), I think is far better than a very unlikely etymology I have seen positing that σαλαμάνδρα is cognate with Basque sugelandila (=“lizard”), sugeandila (“lizard”), etc.⁸

If θάλαμος and θόλος are indeed cognate to Σαλαμής, σαλαμάνδρα, σαλαμίνθη, and σαλάμβη /σαλάβη, then the root would may have begun with the T- sound, as Beekes reconstructs a proto-form *talakya for Ancient Greek θάλασσα, θάλαττα (Attic), θάλαθα (Cretan), σάλασσα (Laconian).

However, I think that the root of Salam- and Thalam- (and probably Tholos as well) began with *k̄ (a palatalized k sound), and all those lexical items were loaned into Proto-Greek from a language where such a sound-shift was regular: for example Thracian, and likely Pelasgian (and Pelasgian may have been very akin to Thracian, but probably not identical, since that would more likely have been noted by an Ancient Greek author).

I posit that the root of Salam- and Thalam- etc. had the oldest meanings “to strike, hit” from where “to bend>to curve” developed, a semantic shift that’s immediately from the real word, for example when a blacksmith strikes not-yet completely hardened metal and makes it bend by striking it. This semantic shift is considered to be attested in, for example, Albanian pjerra, “to bend, incline”, considered to be from the older meaning “to strike, hit, beat” and cognate with Lithuanian periu, perti= “to strike” and Proto-Slavic *pьrьq=“to press”.

So for Salam- and Thalam-, I posit a root similar in form to *kel-m- or *kol-m- (laryngeals, if any, not determined yet; exact vowel not determined, yet, etc.) which meant “to strike, to hit”, and I think that it is the same root from which the Kalm- of Hittite 1) Kalmisna/Kalmisana/Kalmi- meaning “lightning/lightningbolt/thunderbolt; log; firebrand, torch” and 2) Hittite kalmus (“shepherd’s crook”) and 3) Hittite kalmara (“mountain”) derive. θόλος would be from *kel- or *kol-, the “m” of the forms above cited prior being either a suffix-morpheme or else the *kel- or *kol- forms existed parallel and alongside the forms with “m”.

Here are the semantic shifts that I propose for the Hittite words: 1) either “to strike, hit”>“stick, shaft, pole used for striking, hitting”>“lightningbolt/thunderbolt”>“lightning”: see how English “bolt” is considered to very likely derive from PIE *bʰeld- “to knock, strike”, which would make “bolt” (and its Germanic cognates) cognate with Lithuanian beldu (“I knock”) and Lithuanian baldas (“pole used for striking”); or “to strike, hit”>“that which strikes, hits”, which includes a lightningbolt/thunderbolt.

2) “to strike, hit”>“stick, staff used for striking, hitting”>“shepherd’s crook”.

3) “to strike, hit”>“that which is struck”>“mountain (since mountains are so often struck by lightning; see Proto-Germanic *fergunjā “mountain”, by consensus from PIE *perkʷ- “to strike; oak tree (because oak trees are so often struck by lightning)”: if no one has posited that the reason why *fergunjā derives from a root meaning “to strike” is because mountains like oak trees are so often struck by lightning, then I am the first to posit that.

8 See various works published by Corinna Leschber and John Bengtson. Though I don’t like their etymology of salamandra and I think it is certainly wrong, I do enjoy reading most of their linguistics papers, and I thank them for their work.

Do PIE roots with initial **k̑-* yield words beginning with k- in Hittite? Yes they do, as do PIE roots beginning with **k-*: check any decent work on sound-changes from PIE to Hittite. Do roots with initial **k̑-* yield words with initial Z- in Thracian? Yes, see Thracian *zalmon* (“hide, as in a skin of an animal”) from PIE **kel-*, “to cover”: and a S ~ Z vacillation/shift is well-attested in Thracian, both at the beginning of forms (*Zibelsourdos*, *Svelsourdos*, *Salmoxis*, *Zalmoxis*, *Sanis*, *Zanis*, et al.) and within (*Esbenis*, *Ezbenis*).

I haven't yet checked whether PIE **kol-* can yield *kal-* in Hittite, but **kel* can yield *kal-* in Hittite, compare Hittite *iskalla* “to slit, split, tear” from PIE **skólH-ei* ~ **skl̥H-énti* < from PIE **(s)kelH-*/**(s)kelh₂-*/**(s)kelh₃-* /**(s)kel-* meaning “to cut; to split; to separate”.

There is also PIE **kelh₂-* “to stick; prick; stab”, source of Latin *culmus* (“stalk, stem (of grass); hay, straw, thatch”), Ancient Greek *κάλαμος* (“reed”), *κάλαμη* (“reed, stalk, stubble”); Proto-Balto-Slavic **śálʹmāʹ* (“straw”), Proto-Germanic **halmaz* (“halm, stem, stalk; straw; hay”). Kroonen, who adds Lithuanian *kelmas* (“tree trunk”) as a cognate, reconstructs the original athematic paradigm as **kélh₂-m̥* ~ **kl̥h₂-m-ós* (cf. **elm*, **alm*, **ulm* (“elm”)), rejecting Beekes' **kólh₂-m̥* ~ **kl̥h₂-ém-*.

It's interesting that if I'm right about *Salamis* = “lizard” coming from “to curve, bend” and in turn from “to strike, hit”, then that chimes with the *kol-* of *κόλουρος* (*κόλουρος* is the source of *Koulouri*---the alternative, newer name of the island of *Salamis*). Because the *kol-* of *κόλος* (“docked”) is probably unanimously considered to derive from a root that meant “to strike, hit”, leading to “that which has been struck, chopped > docked”. Ancient Greek *κόλος* has been proposed to be cognate with Lithuanian *kálti* = “to hammer, to strike”; Latvian *kalt* = “to hammer, to peck, to chisel, to hew”; Proto-Slavic **kòlти* “to stab, to sting” (from **kolh₂-* from PIE **kelh₂-* “to beat, to break”); Ancient Greek *κελεῖς* “axe”; Lithuanian *kulti*, “to hit”; Latvian *kult* (“to hit”), the *-cello* of Latin *percello*, “to strike, to smite” (PIE **kelh₂-* “to beat, to strike”).

Do those Hittite *kalm-* words that I discussed earlier derive from a root with an initial **k̑* or an initial *k*? In order for those Hittite words to be cognate with the *Salm/Zalm* of *Salmoxis/Zalmoxis*, the Hittite words may have to derive from a root with **k̑* onset rather than with *k*, because I recall examples where initial *K* in Dacian remained *K* and was not sibilized: for my next update, I will try to find data concerning that, and I will try to find out what some of the references on Hittite say about the etymology of those Hittite words beginning with *Kalm-* that I discussed earlier; I recall that I've seen a source from over three decades ago that derived at least some of those Hittite *kalm-* words from PIE **(s)kel-*, “to split, separate, part, divide”, which sounds very wrong to me.

Armenian *sal* (“slab; flagstone; anvil”) and Old Armenian *sal* (“slab; flagstone; sheet of metal; anvil”) is obviously from “to strike, hit, beat, hammer”, from there also developing the meaning “something hard and flat that was flattened/shaped by hard blows from a hard tool”. The PIE root for Armenian/Old Armenian *sal* has been reconstructed as **k̑HI-* by some sources.

Part 3---*Salmoxis/Zalmoxis* = “Hurler of Lightning”

So it is from the root of Hittite *Kalmi* = “lightning”, a root that I think meant “to strike, hit” that I also derive the *Salm-/Zalm-* in Thracian *Σάλμοξις / Ζάλμοξις*: I conclude (due to

additional factors that I will detail) that Salm-/Zalm="Lightning" and most likely derives from a root meaning "to strike, hit", as does Hittite Kalmisna/Kalmisana="Lightning bolt, log".

Possibly instead, Salm/Zalm="Lightning" derives from PIE *ǵʰelh₃-/*ǵʰelh₂- "to flourish; to shine, green, yellow", since I have seen that probably most "lightning" words derive from "bright"--- but I have seen no words meaning "lightning" deriving from that *ǵʰelh₃-/*ǵʰelh₂- root and we already have Hittite Kalmi="lightning", and I conclude that the Thracian form is much more likely cognate with the Hittite Kalmi-, which phonologically cannot be from PIE *ǵʰelh₃-/*ǵʰelh₂-. So I conclude that Salm-/Zalm- in Salmoxis/Zalmoxis more likely comes from "to strike, to hit", a root that I have outlined above in Part 2 of this paper.

In Herodotus' Histories, the oldest surviving text/writing of any kind yet found where the Geto-Dacian/Thracian theonym Σάλμοξις / Ζάλμοξις is attested, Σάλμοξις / Ζάλμοξις was stated to be the same as Gebeleixis/Zebeleixis, a Geto-Dacian/Thracian deity corresponding to the Greek Zeus. See also this quote from Herodotus, The Histories, 4:94: "Furthermore, when there is thunder and lightning these same Thracians shoot arrows skyward as a threat to the god..."--Herodotus is speaking of Zalmoxis when he refers to "the god"; see the entire excerpt in my note here: ⁹.

Zalmoxis in most manuscripts appears as Salmoxis, and I will use Salmoxis primarily in this article. The form "Zamolxis" found in later corrupted manuscripts (you can check the literature on the subject) is an erroneous form, as I will detail.

Zalmoxis/Salmoxis was the Geto-Daco-Thracian thunder, lightning, rain and sky-god; the later tradition of a mortal Zalmoxis and his excellent teachings came later, and I will not discuss that Zalmoxis in this paper, only because it has no bearing on the etymology. Salmoxis/Zalmoxis was not an earth god, and Salmoxis/Zalmoxis has nothing to do with any Zam- words meaning "earth" with derive from PIE *dʰéǵʰōm, "earth".

Since many years back, I have concluded that the Zamolxis/Samolxis (not sure if any manuscripts have Samolxis; but the Zamolxis variant is attested in a number of manuscripts) forms are erroneous, and since many years back I have concluded that a Baltic comparanda, Lithuanian Zameluks, a cthonic (earth) god (whose name has some variant forms, I recall; and I know that none have Zalm-) that Cless in 1852 thought Salmoxis/Zalmoxis may be cognate with is not cognate with Zalmoxis/Salmoxis at all. There remains a slight possibility that the forms Zamolxis/Samolxis are distinct names having a different etymology, but that will depend on whether "-xis" has any legitimacy as a bonafide Thracian element at the end of words/names. On the other hand, instead, I have found that -oxis has 100% legitimacy, as I will show in this paper.

9 Herodotus, *The Histories*, 4.94: from which I quote (A.D. Godley English translation, 1920): "Their belief in their immortality is as follows: they believe that they do not die, but that one who perishes goes to the deity Salmoxis, or Gebeleĩzis, as some of them call him. Once every five years they choose one of their people by lot and send him as a messenger to Salmoxis, with instructions to report their needs; and this is how they send him: three lances are held by designated men; others seize the messenger to Salmoxis by his hands and feet, and swing and toss him up on to the spear-points. If he is killed by the toss, they believe that the god regards them with favor; but if he is not killed, they blame the messenger himself, considering him a bad man, and send another messenger in place of him. It is while the man still lives that they give him the message. Furthermore, when there is thunder and lightning these same Thracians shoot arrows skyward as a threat to the god, believing in no other god but their own."

Since many years back I have also rejected a folk etymology from Porphyrios, born in Tyre, which is in present-day Lebanon, who wrote in his *Life of Pythagoras* (written in the 3rd century AD) that Salmoxis/Zalmoxis derive from a Thracian word *zalmos/zalmus* (“hide of an animal”), a Thracian word that used in some now lost Ancient Greek literature (as we see from the fact that it appears in Hesychios of Alexandria’s Glossary of Ancient Greek) and thereby became much more well-known to Non-Thracians than the Thracian *Zalm-/Salm-* word that meant “Lightning”, which was unknown to Porphyrios of Lebanon in the 3rd century AD. Porphyrios’ statement is explained by his acquaintance with the Thracian *zalmus/zalmob* (“hide of an animal”) word from Greek literature; his ignorance of the lightning *Salm/Zalm* word; and his acquaintance with a tradition that the mortal Zalmoxis/Salmoxis was wrapped in a bear’s skin after birth. We have no verification that the Thunder god was believed to have been wrapped in a bear skin at birth as well, but there may have been such a tradition as well.

So leave aside the PIE *d^héǵh²ōm, “earth” derivation and the “(bear) hide” derivation (which would be from PIE *kel, “hide, skin” maybe in turn from “to cover”). Salmoxis/Zalmoxis was not an earth-god nor did his name contain a reference to bear’s hide nor to “to protect” nor “to cover” (storm clouds do cover the sky, but PIE *kel may have no derivatives referring to cloud-cover; and even if it does, that’s a coincidence).

Salmoxis/Zalmoxis in fact most likely meant “Lightning-Hurler”, with *Salm/Zalm*=“Lightning” and *οξίς*=“Hurler, Thrower, Emitter”, from “to drive out, push out, to throw, to hurl, to give off/emit” from 1) PIE *h₂e²ks- “axis; axle<to drive”, in turn from PIE *h₂eǵ- “to drive”; 2) or from PIE *h₂eǵ- s-, in turn from PIE *h₂eǵ- “to drive”. A phonological development paralleling PIE *h₂e²ks > Thracian *οξίς* is seen with the phonological development of PIE *h₂e²k- “sharp” > Ancient Greek *ὀξύς*=“sharp” (among many other sharp-related meanings of *ὀξύς* in Ancient Greek). I will further detail this etymology later in this paper. First I will relate the tale of *Σαλμωνεύς*.

That *Salm/Zalm*=“lightning” is extremely likely indicated by the name *Σαλμωνεύς* which was the name of a very lightning-associated figure from Greek mythology.

In Greek mythology, Salmoneus (Ancient Greek: *Σαλμωνεύς*) was 'the wicked' eponymous king and founder of *Salmone* in *Pisatis*. Salmoneus was formerly a *Thessalian* prince as son of King *Aeolus* of *Aeolia*. His mother was identified as *Enarete*, daughter of *Deimachus*, or *Iphis*, daughter of *Peneus*, or *Laodice*, daughter of *Aloeus*. Salmoneus's first wife was *Alcidice* by whom he became the father of *Tyro*, while his second wife was *Sidero*.

Emigrating from Aeolis with a number of Aeolians, Salmoneus founded a city in Eleia (Elis) on the banks of the river *Alpheius* and called it *Salmonia* after his own name. He then married *Alcidice*, the daughter of *Aleus* but when she died, the king took for a second wife *Sidero* who treated his beautiful daughter *Tyro* unkindly.

Salmoneus and his brother *Sisyphus* hated each other (Salmoneus in the myths is said to have had quite a number of brothers). *Sisyphus* found out from an *oracle* that if he married *Tyro*, she would bear him children who would kill Salmoneus. At first, *Tyro* submitted to *Sisyphus*, married him, and bore him a son. When *Tyro* found out what the child would do to Salmoneus, she killed the boy. It was soon after this that *Tyro* lay with *Poseidon* and bore him *Pelias* and *Neleus*.

Salmoneus, being an overbearing man and impious, came to be hated by his subjects for he ordered them to worship him under the name of *Zeus*. He built a bridge of brass, over which he drove at full speed in his chariot to imitate thunder, the effect being heightened by dried skins and cauldrons

trailing behind while torches were thrown into the air to represent lightning. For this sin of hubris, Zeus eventually struck him down with his thunderbolt and destroyed the town.

“And he [i.e. Salmoneus] acted profanely, by casting torches (in the air) as if they were lightnings,
And dragging dried hides with kettles at his chariot,
Pretending to make thunder, so he was thunderstruck by Zeus.”

According to Frazer, the early Greek kings, who were expected to produce rain for the benefit of the crops, were in the habit of imitating thunder and lightning in the character of Zeus. At [Crannon in Thessaly](#), there was a bronze chariot which in time of drought was shaken and prayers offered for rain. S. Reinach suggests that the story that Salmoneus was struck by lightning was due to the misinterpretation of a picture, in which a Thessalian magician appeared bringing down lightning and rain from heaven. Hence arose the idea that he was the victim of the anger or jealousy of Zeus and that the picture represented his punishment.

In addition to this Ancient Greek (and Thracian?) myth of Salmoneus, there is also a depiction on an Attic red-figure column crater, dated to the first half of the 5th century BC, of a man identified as Salmoneus¹⁰ and wielding a three-pronged lightning-symbol object in one hand and an uplifted sword in his other hand, as he stands next to Iris, goddess of the rainbows: rainbows which of course often appear after a rainstorm.

The myth of Salmoneus and the Attic red figure artwork depicting Salmoneus in such way, indicate to me that Salm- has to do with lightning and the storm-god, as we see in Herodotus' Histories 4: 94 that Salmoxis is described as a god of lightning. This Salm- in Salmoneus I conclude derives from Thracian and is the same Salm- seen in Salmoxis, a Salm- which meant “lightning”. The -oneus portion of Salmoneus is encountered also in Othruoneus, Alkuoneus, et al.

The Gebel-/Zebel of Gebeleixis/Zebeleixis/Gebeleizis/Zebeleizis¹¹ meant “Lightning/javelin/arrow” and probably is cognate to English gavel as well as to javelin. For now I refer the reader to my other published works on the etymology of Gebeleixis/Zebeleixis/Gebeleizis/Zebeleizis. The attestation Beleixis (or Beleizis) for Gebelexis is probably from a Thracian Bel=lightning bolt, javelin, missile, from PIE **g^welH-* “to throw”, compare Ancient Greek βέλος “missile, arrow, dart” from the same root; so Beleixis meant “Lightning/arrow/spear-thrower/Emitter/propeller”, with lightning bolts interchangeable with arrows and javelins, spears. Back in 2004 or early 2005 I first thought that Beleixis meant “Lightning/spear-thrower” but back then I couldn't find a root for -eixis with such meanings, then I 90% forgot about that early etymology of mine. The variant Nebeleixis may be an error from the person who wrote the ancient manuscript. Or Nebel may be a parallel form of Gebel from a parallel root.

My previous theory was that Salmoxis/Zalmoxis and Gebeleixis/Zebeleixis (etc.) and Zibelthiurdos/Svelsourdos (etc.) all meant “Striker of the Oak” (no one posited

10 Identified as Salmoneus by the scholar Carl Robert in 1903, the ancient artwork can be seen here: [Salmoneus AJA 1899 - Salmoneus - Wikipedia](#)

11 Nebeleixis or Nebeleizis, and Beleixis or Beleizis are attested as well, very likely corruptions, corruptions occurring either in the writing stage or in the spoken stage.

that before me), but I conclude that in fact Salmoxis/Zalmoxis and Gebeleixis/Zebeleixis meant “Lightning-Hurler” (no one posited that before me either, but “Lightning-Hurler” has been posited for Zibelthiurdos/Svelsurdos, to name two variants of that theonym). “Striker of the oak” is very likely as well because oak trees were the trees most often struck by lightning in Europe, and hence oak trees were the trees of Zeus, Jupiter, Thor, and the other equivalents in Europe. But “Lightning-hurler” is better because it doesn’t limit itself to oak trees, so that is a semantic advantage of “Lightning-Hurler”. From what I’ve seen, what will settle the question is whether Zalm/Salm and Gebel/Zebel meant “to strike, to hit> to chop” or “lightning” (in turn from “to strike, to hit, to chop” or from “bright”, the two different options coming from two unrelated roots). Gebel/Zebel more likely meant “Lightning”, not “to strike, hit, chop”, though even if Gebel meant “lightning”, it likely derived from the earlier meanings “to strike, hit, chop”: otherwise, it’s likely from “bright”.

Zibelthiurods/Svelsurdos meant either “Lightning-Hurler” or “Lightning-holder”, and both of those options have already been proposed for that theonym and its variants.

I conclude that I have confirmation from ἀπροξίς and from many other linguistic evidences (including quite a number that I didn’t discuss in this version) that οξίς meant “Hurler, Thrower, Emitter”, from “Driver”, from PIE *h₂éks-, “axle, axis<to drive” or from PIE *h₂éǵ-s-, both forms deriving in turn from PIE *h₂éǵ-, “to drive”.

The eixis/eizis of Gebeleixis/Gebeleizis (etc.) may be from *h₂éks- or *h₂éǵ-s- as well, or from *h₂eyks-, a new variant that I propose; or from *h₂eyǵ-s-, “thrown, hurled”, from *h₂eyǵ-, “to drive” (I have seen that a PIE *h₂eyǵ- “to drive” is already proposed to have existed besides the more common *h₂éǵ- “to drive”). Later in this paper I will discuss my theory that PIE *h₂eyǵ- “oak tree” derives from “Lightning bolt”, from “thrown, hurled”, because oak trees are the trees in Europe most often struck by lightning. And PIE *h₂eyǵ- “goat” is very likely from “driven”, referring to shepherds driving along herds of goats.

For the Daco-Thracian development of PIE *h₂eyǵ- “oak tree”, I have this data so far: the Dacian toponyms Aizisis and Aigidava: the Aiz/Aig could derive from PIE *h₂eyǵ- “goat” or from PIE *h₂eyǵ- “oak tree”: these two PIE words were sonically/phonetically identical. Based on those Dacian toponyms, PIE *h₂eyǵ- “oak tree” very likely had the form Aiz or Ais or Aig or Aiks in Daco-Thracian, or all the above in various Daco-Thracian idioms (as we see Gebeleiξίς/Gebeleixis and Gebeleizis), perhaps at least sometimes with a suffix “-is” (Aizis, Aisis, Aigis) or with another suffix; or with different suffixes in different dialects/idioms¹². However, the eixis/eizis of

12 Like Ancient Greek, Daco-Thracian quite surely had more than one word for the oak tree, and Romanian stejar (“oak tree”; the only Romanian word for the oak tree that I know of, besides gorun for the Sessile Oak) and Romanian gorun (Quercus petraea, the Sessile Oak) have been posited as likely deriving from Daco-Thracian rather than from Slavic: if so, then Bulgarian stežer, “pole, oak tree” and Bulgarian stež, “white oak” and Bulgarian gorun, “Durmast oak” and Serbo-Croatian gorun (“holm oak”) would also be from Daco-Thracian: either directly from a Non-Romance and Non-Slavic population or via early Romanians who would have had (and still have, but surely more back then) many Paleo-Balkan words, including some Daco-Thracian words, in their mostly Latin-derived language, which was brought by the Romans from Italy. Some ancient Italic peoples, including of the Latini/Roman ethnic group, are among the ancestors of some Romanians, and some are also among the ancestors of some other Balkan people,

Gebeleiξίς/Gebeleizis very likely derives from an earlier *h₂eyǵ-s- form, so it's also very likely that *h₂eyǵ- "oak tree" could have become Eig/Eiz/Eis in the idioms/dialects from where Gebeleixis/Gebeleizis derive from. So the *h₂ey- of *h₂eyǵ- "oak tree" most likely became Ai- in at least some dialects of Daco-Thracian, and likely became Ei- in some other dialects; and *h₂ey- could perhaps even have become O- in some dialects, as we see English "oak" and οξίς in Salmoxis/Zalmoxis.

The ~ks~ development that we see in Proto-Germanic *aiks , "oak tree" may not have come about in Daco-Thracian, but it may have, especially since the ~ks~ most likely (since PIE *h₂eyǵ- "goat" became αἴξ "goat" in Ancient Greek, and because we find αἰγίλωψ / aigíλωψ meaning "the Turkey oak tree" or "the Valonia oak tree" in Ancient Greek) came about in the Ancient Greek derivative of PIE *h₂eyǵ- "oak tree" as well, since it has been posited that the aigí- of aigíλωψ is from an unattested *αἴξ (*aíx) "oak tree", which, given αἴξ = "she-goat; goat" in Ancient Greek, was most likely not borrowed by the Greeks from Thracian: more likely the Greeks had it from PIE, even though otherwise we do not find any derivatives of PIE *h₂eyǵ- "oak tree" in Ancient Greek; PIE *h₂eyǵ- "goat" is on the other-hand well represented in Ancient Greek and Greek.

I posit that it's possible that PIE *h₂eyǵ- "oak tree" derives from "Lightning bolt", from "Thrown, Hurlled", from PIE *h₂eyǵ- "to drive". In fact, I now think that that is so, because, as noted earlier, oak trees are scientifically confirmed to be the trees in Europe most often struck by lightning, due to their high water content, and from ancient mythologies and traditions, we know that ancient peoples of Europe knew very well that oak trees were the trees most often struck by lightning. While PIE *h₂eyǵ- "goat" likely derives from "driven" instead of "thrown, hurled": "driven" in reference to the shepherds driving herds of goats about to graze. I think this etymology for PIE *h₂eyǵ- "goat" has already been posited, but not the one for oak tree. Polysemy is common in ancient and old and recent IE languages: there's a lot of polysemy in Sanskrit. So it's no problem for *h₂eyǵ- to have meant both "driven" and "thrown, hurled", since both sets of meanings derive from "to drive", and the shift from "driven, propelled" to "thrown, hurled" is a simple shift.

In my next update, I will also discuss my theory that Pelasgos="Lightning-Thrower" and was an old name for the Zeus of the Pelasgians. With Pel="Lightning" (see Ancient Greek πέλεκυς = "two-edged axe for felling trees; battle-axe; exuctioner's axe") and Asgos="Thrower", from a root that I will detail next time.

Part 4: κορίαννον / κορίανδρον / κορίαμβλον / koriandnon / koriadnon

After trying out numerous scenarios since early 2019, my conclusion is that Ancient Greek κορίαννον / κορίανδρον / κορίαμβλον / koriandnon/ koriadnon comes from Pre-Greek Kori="seed" and Pre-Greek Andnon="round", so κορίαννον / κορίανδρον / κορίαμβλον / koriandnon/ koriadnon="round seed", referring to the round, rather large and very conspicuous seeds of the coriander plant, seeds which were as important as consuming the plant itself.

including various South Slavic ethnic groups, Albanians, Greeks, and others.

I conclude that my hypothetical Kori="seed" derives from a root meaning "to sprout, to rise"; possibly the root is PIE * $\acute{k}er$ - "to grow"; from * $\acute{k}er$ - "to grow" may also derive (not necessarily via a Hellenic language) Ancient Greek κόρυς ("helmet") and the Ancient Greek/Pre-Greek city-name Κόρινθος (Korinthos>Corinth), which is already thought to most likely have been named after the hill of Korinthos. The short form κόριον for κορίαννον / κορίανδρον / κορίαμβλον / koriandnon/ koriadnon was likely simply an abbreviation, as the 1940 LSJ states; if not treated as simply an abbreviation, κόριον would have meant "the seed/the seed (plant)" if my etymology is correct: given the great importance of the coriander seeds to the ancient Aegean people and others, that makes a lot of sense and works very well.

This Pre-Greek language was a kind of IE language, either descending from PIE or from a brother/sister language of PIE. I will add more details about this etymology in the next update/enlargement of this paper, coming soon.

A.G., January 5th 2024